

Male and female helper effects on maternal investment and adult survival in red-winged fairy-wrens

Journal:	<i>Behavioral Ecology</i>
Manuscript ID	Draft
Manuscript Type:	Original article
Keywords:	Cooperative breeding, Maternal investment, Egg size, <i>Malurus elegans</i> , Survival

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1 **Male and female helper effects on maternal investment and adult survival in red-winged**
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3 **fairy-wrens**

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5 **Running header: costs and benefits of helpers**
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10 **Abstract**
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12 Despite its importance for the evolution of cooperative breeding, it has proven difficult to determine
13 whether helpers improve their recipients' fitness. Helpers affect fitness in multiple ways, both
14 positive and negative, but their effects can also be concealed through reduced maternal investment.
15 Furthermore, determining the direction of causation is difficult, as helper presence may indicate a
16 productive territory, rather than high productivity indicating an effect of help. In cooperatively
17 breeding red-winged fairy-wrens (*Malurus elegans*) groups reduce care when they have male
18 helpers, but groups with female helpers do not, so nestlings receive more food. Thus our predictions
19 vary with helper sex rather than helper number, and by studying within-group changes with regard
20 to group composition we separate phenotypically plastic responses from among-group correlations.
21 Females did not reduce egg size in response to an increasing number of female helpers. However,
22 more male or female helpers allowed females to lay larger clutches and more female helpers
23 reduced re-nesting intervals. There was mixed support for a benefit of load-lightening: helpers, but
24 not breeders, gained survival benefits with increasing number of male helpers. However, increased
25 competition counterbalanced these male helper benefits, and survival decreased with the number of
26 female helpers. We also found consistent among-group differences, which would have erroneously
27 been interpreted as helper effects had we not disentangled the within-group changes with regard to
28 group composition. This study highlights the importance of assessing carers' benefits in relation to
29 both group composition and size, and of investigating the within-individual plastic response of
30 helper effects.
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57 **Key-words:** Cooperative breeding, Maternal investment, Egg size, *Malurus elegans*, Survival
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Introduction

Cooperative breeding is often considered paradoxical because some individuals assist others to rear offspring instead of breeding on their own (Brown 1987). Much focus has been on determining how helpers improve the fitness of their beneficiaries, since such a positive effect is necessary to explain cooperative breeding through kin selection (Emlen 1995) or group augmentation (Kokko et al. 2001). Helpers can increase overall parental effort so that offspring receive greater total care (additive care; e.g. Clutton-Brock et al. 2001; Doerr and Doerr 2007), which can increase offspring growth (Hodge 2005) or productivity of the dominant breeders (Emlen and Wrege 1991; Kingma et al. 2010; Meade et al. 2010). Helpers can also reduce the workload of the breeders (load-lightening; e.g. Hatchwell and Russell 1996; Legge 2000; Balshine et al. 2001), which can increase their subsequent survival (Russell and Rowley 1988; Cockburn et al. 2008; Paquet et al. 2015) or reduce intervals between reproductive attempts (Woxvold and Magrath 2005; Blackmore and Heinsohn 2007). Overall, there is thus ample potential for helpers to not only have short-term effects on current reproduction, but also long-term effects on future reproduction (Brouwer et al. 2012).

Despite the potential for great benefits, helper effects on offspring growth and survival are often weak or absent (Griffin and West 2003; Woxvold and Magrath 2005; Canestrari et al. 2008). To explain this paradox, it has recently been suggested that helper benefits can also be concealed by compensatory maternal investment (Russell et al. 2007). Females adjusting the size or quality of their eggs can save energy without necessarily reducing their reproductive success, because helper investment is likely to compensate for the “bad start” suffered by the offspring (Russell and Lummaa 2009). Females could reallocate energy from immediate reproduction to future survival or reproductive success, thus improving long-term fitness, and recent findings suggest that this phenomenon is widespread among cooperative breeders (Russell et al. 2007; Taborsky et al. 2007; Canestrari et al. 2011; Santos and Macedo 2011; Paquet et al. 2013; but see: Koenig et al. 2009).

Despite intense focus on the potential benefits of helpers, there might also be costs associated with the presence of helpers, for example due to intra-specific competition for resources

1 (Newton 1992). Such negative density-dependence could cause individuals living in larger groups
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4 to survive worse than individuals in small groups (Brouwer et al. 2006). Theory has long recognised
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6 that living with kin can be costly (Hamilton 1964; West et al. 2001), but the possibility that costs
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8 imposed by helpers have important fitness consequences has been neglected empirically.
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10 The costs and benefits of helper presence can vary with the sex or state of the helpers. For
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12 example, one sex may invest more in care than the other, as it is more likely for them to survive and
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14 inherit dominance status (Clutton-Brock et al. 2006). The amount of care an individual provides
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16 varies not only with the state of the individual itself, but also depends on the investment of the other
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18 group members. Group composition (i.e. the type of individuals) can thus have important fitness
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20 consequences for each group member in addition to the effects of group size. This aspect has only
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22 recently be emphasized (Brouwer et al. 2014a), although some studies have shown that reproductive
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24 success is positively associated with only one sex of helpers (Brooker and Rowley 1995; Legge
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26 2000; Koenig et al. 2011) and therefore suggest that the effect of helpers on fitness components
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28 should be estimated for each type (e.g. sex) of helper separately.
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33 In this study we investigate whether and how helpers benefit their group members in the
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35 cooperatively breeding red-winged fairy-wren (*Malurus elegans*), a species where both males and
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37 females are highly philopatric and usually stay in their natal territory for at least one year to assist
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39 the dominant breeders (Rowley et al. 1988). More specifically we investigate (I) whether breeding
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41 females show load-lightening via egg investment, (II) whether helpers allow females to re-nest
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43 more rapidly after nest failure and (III) whether helpers affect the survival of breeders and of other
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45 helpers present in the group.
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48 A difficulty with determining helper effects is that experimental manipulation of group size
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50 is complicated. This is not just because enlarging group size is usually impossible, but also because
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52 reducing group size might lead to undesirable side effects, like social disruption or abandonment of
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54 the current reproductive attempt by the dominant female (Cockburn 1998). Observational data have
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56 the disadvantage that it is difficult to determine causality of positive correlations between helper
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1 number and fitness components such as reproductive success. High-quality breeders or breeders
2 living in high-quality territories might also produce high-quality offspring and be more likely to
3 have helpers because of past reproductive success (Cockburn 1998). Two features of our study
4 system help us to distinguish whether any correlations are reflecting the causal relationship of the
5 hypothesis or not. First, in red-winged fairy-wrens, previous work has shown that all group
6 members reduced their provisioning rates in response to an increasing number of male helpers
7 (load-lightening). However, an increase in the number of female helpers within the group did not
8 reduce the *per capita* investment of the group members (additive care, Brouwer et al. 2014a). As a
9 result, with an increasing number of female helpers, nestlings received more food, grew larger, and
10 had a higher post-fledging survival. In contrast, an increasing number of male helpers was not
11 associated with offspring growth or survival. These findings mean that our predictions of helper
12 effects will vary with the sex of the helpers, while the alternative hypothesis of confounded inter-
13 correlations between territory quality and group size predicts that results will be independent of the
14 sex of the helpers. Second, by studying the same individuals over multiple seasons with variable
15 group composition we are able to separate whether effects are due to a phenotypically plastic
16 response due to a change in helper number within groups rather than non-causal correlations due to
17 large groups being associated with high territory quality. Comparisons of the same group with and
18 without helpers have been criticized as groups where helper numbers change might be a biased
19 sample of the population (Dickinson & Hatchwell 2004), as changes in helper number are the result
20 of high reproduction or low survival. However, here we do not only compare groups with and
21 without helpers, but rather analyse the change in number of helpers of each sex within the same
22 group in addition to between-group differences.

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Consequently, we predict that (Ia) breeding females should decrease the size of their eggs in response to an increasing number of female but not male helpers, since any negative effects of egg size on offspring will be compensated for by the extra care received in the presence of female helpers (Figure 1a); (Ib) an increase in male and female helpers should allow breeding females to

1 lay larger clutches, because the increased total parental effort allows more chicks to be provisioned
2 (Figure 1b); (II) the time-interval between nest failure and a replacement clutch should be smaller
3 with more male helpers if the previous nest reached the nestling stage, since breeding females will
4 have been able to reduce their provisioning rates in the presence of males (Figure 1a); (IIIa) survival
5 of all adult members of the group should be higher with an increasing number of male, but not
6 female, helpers due to load-lightening at the nestling stage (Figure 1c); (IIIb) survival of female
7 breeders should also be higher with an increasing number female helpers, if breeder females
8 decrease their egg size in the presence of female helpers as predicted under Ia (Figure 1e). It should
9 be noted that the overall survival response to the number of helpers needs not be positive, as intra-
10 group competition may outweigh any benefits of load-lightening (i.e. we only predict that the
11 association between the number of female helpers and survival is more negative (or less positive)
12 than between the number of male helpers and survival) (Figure 1d & 1f).

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Methods

Data collection

Data were collected in Smithbrook Nature Reserve in Western Australia (116.10°E, 34.20°S) between 2008 and 2015. The main study area comprises ~65 territories in which >99% of the adult birds were individually color-banded. Those territories were checked at least fortnightly for group composition, survival and breeding activity throughout the breeding season (Oct-Jan). Once nests were found they were checked at least twice a week to collect data on egg-laying date, number of eggs, hatchlings and fledglings and in order to color-band all offspring. Female fairy-wrens re-nest after failure and can initiate as many as four clutches, but only in exceptional cases rear two broods to independence in a season (Russell and Rowley 2000). Starvation of nestlings is negligible, but nest predation is high (Brouwer et al. 2014a).

Eighty-eight percent of the border of the reserve is bounded by unsuitable habitat (farmland), but three narrow corridors lead away from the reserve allowing for dispersal to the surrounding state forests (Brouwer et al. 2014b). From 2009 onwards each year 50-220 territories in the areas surrounding the main study area were monitored and checked for dispersers (up to 2km radius). Long-distance dispersal is extremely rare (median distance = 150m, mean territory width = 103 ± 27 SD, N=20), and considering the spatial configuration of our main study area, this indicates that we can accurately estimate survival consequences for both males and females.

The sex of adult red-winged fairy-wrens can easily be determined using plumage characteristics (Rowley et al. 1988). Social status was determined from behavioural observations, plumage variation and age (Russell and Rowley 2000; Brouwer et al. 2011), with each group comprising a 'dominant' pair-bonded male and female and from zero to eight subordinate male and/or female helpers (mean group size = 3.8 ± 1.3 S.D., N= 65). Both males and females stay and help their parents for at least one year, but females disperse on average earlier than males, which means that 32-42% of helpers were female each year. Nest watches have shown that both male and female helpers provision the young at a similar rate (Brouwer et al. 2014a). Occasionally an

1 individual joins another group and does not provision (~1.5% of all birds, usually females); these
2 birds were not considered helpers here.
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5 During the seasons 2009-2013, length and width of eggs were measured using callipers with
6 an accuracy of 0.01 mm. Egg size, quantified as the egg volume, was estimated as length \times width²
7 \times 0.51 (Hoyt 1979). The interval between nests after nest failure until a new clutch was laid, was
8 calculated using the following method: when a nest was found during the laying phase the date the
9 first egg was laid (= lay date) was estimated assuming that one egg is laid per day. When a nest was
10 found during the incubation phase lay date was back-calculated once the eggs hatched to produce
11 nestlings, assuming an incubation period of 15 days with incubation starting when the last egg was
12 laid (Rowley et al. 1988). If a nest was found incubating but was depredated before nestlings were
13 observed, we estimated the average lay date from the earliest and latest possible lay date, taking the
14 number of days the nest had been incubated, clutch size and the incubation period into account.
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31 *Statistical analyses*

32 We investigated helper effects on the four response variables: egg volume, clutch size, re-nest
33 interval after nest failure, and annual adult survival probability. For the egg volume, clutch size and
34 re-nest interval analyses, we used general(ized) linear mixed models (GLMMs), in which a breeder
35 female's identity was fitted as a random effect (intercept) to account for non-independence of the
36 data, as we collected data on the same birds over different years. In the survival analysis we
37 included the territory identifier as a random intercept, as the survival of birds from the same
38 territory might not be independent.
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48 Repeated observations of the same breeder female or territory with varying group size and
49 composition allows us to disentangle within- (i.e. plastic behavioral response to changing number of
50 helpers) from between-subject effects of group composition, using a widely used mixed modeling
51 technique called within-subject centering (van de Pol and Wright 2009). In short, this method splits
52 up the effect of helper numbers into two helper number predictor variables: the within-subject
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1 centred (within-subject effect) and mean number (between-subject effect) of female and male
2 helpers. In the analyses of egg volume, clutch size and re-nest interval, the number of (fe)male
3 helpers is centred around the mean number of (fe)male helpers a dominant female had during the
4 study period, whereas for the survival analysis it is centred around the mean per territory. In all
5 analyses, the centred and mean effects were included as continuous covariates.
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12 We analysed the effects of helpers on the survival of all group members (males, females,
13 breeders and helpers) in a single model and hence the sex and social status (breeder/helper) of the
14 birds and their interactions were included as fixed categorical covariates in this analysis. To test
15 whether the effect of the number of male and female helpers differed from each other we did a post-
16 hoc test: the number of male and female helpers were substituted for group size, after which the
17 Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) values of both of these non-nested models were compared
18 (Akaike 1973; Burnham and Anderson 2003). Annual adult survival was estimated for all 671
19 individuals in the main study area between November 2008 and November 2015. A preliminary
20 capture-mark-recapture survival analysis in program MARK (White and Burnham 1999) showed
21 that for individuals in the main study area the detection probability is 100% (i.e. there were no
22 individuals that were not seen in one year that were observed in later years). Consequently, for final
23 analysis we switched to known fate analysis in which survival to the next year was fitted as a binary
24 variable using a logit-link function and binomial error.
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42 Mean egg volume and clutch size were fitted using a multivariate mixed model to account
43 for covariance between egg and clutch size, since a trade-off between egg and clutch size is
44 common in birds (Williams 2001). Clutch and egg size data were available for 292 clutches from
45 108 females. Since there is limited variation in clutch size (98% were 2 or 3 egg clutches), clutch
46 size was transformed into a binary variable, with small clutches (1-2 eggs) being coded as 0 and
47 large clutches (3 eggs) coded as 1. Clutch size was fitted using a logit link function and binomial
48 error distribution, whereas egg volume was fitted using an identity link function and Gaussian error
49 distribution. The re-nest interval was determined for 267 replacement clutches, in 119 females, and
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2 calculated as the number of days it took for a new nest to be initiated and clutch to be laid after nest
3 failure, and fitted using an identity link function and Gaussian error distribution.
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6 Several additional variables were included in some or all the models to account for their
7 separate confounding effect on the fitness related traits, or to investigate whether they modified the
8 effect of the number of helpers by including their interaction terms. Specifically, year and prior
9 breeding experience of the breeder female (coded yes/no) were included as fixed categorical
10 variables in the analyses on egg volume, clutch size and re-nest interval. Whether the previous nest
11 reached the nestling phase (coded yes/no) was included as a fixed factor in the re-nest interval
12 analysis. Egg and clutch size typically show seasonal trends in birds (Crick et al. 1993). Therefore,
13 rainfall and day of season were also included in the egg and clutch size analysis. In order to
14 determine the time periods during which mean daily rainfall significantly explained these traits we
15 used a sliding-window approach implemented in R package climwin (van de Pol and Cockburn
16 2011; Bailey and van de Pol 2015). We found that the critical time-window for rainfall fell between
17 60-12 days before laying, and thus calculated the amount of rainfall over this period for each clutch.
18 Since larger females may lay larger eggs, we included tarsus size of the breeding female. To correct
19 for possible observer biases the identity of the observer measuring the eggs was also included in the
20 analysis.
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39 Except for the multivariate analysis on egg volume and clutch size (see above), statistical
40 analyses were performed in R3.1.2 (R Development Core Team 2014) using package lme4 (Bates et
41 al. 2011). We used Akaike's information criterion, corrected for the sample size (AICc), to select the
42 most parsimonious model. Models that are better supported by the data result in lower AICc values.
43 We used an all-subset approach in which all possible models with the parameters of interest were
44 run using package MuMIn (Bartoń 2015), but we report the eight top models within $\Delta AICc$ of two
45 units of the best supported model only. The fact that the analysis of egg volume and clutch size was
46 multivariate with two different link functions imposed a technical constraint that did not allow us to
47 follow the same procedure as above. Hence, model selection was performed through stepwise
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1 backward elimination of non-significant fixed terms ($\alpha = 0.10$) based on likelihood ratio tests in
2 MLWin2.32 (Rasbash et al. 2005). All terms were added to final model to confirm non-significance
3 and reported effect sizes are derived from final models.
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10 **Results**

11 *Helper effects on maternal egg investment*

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13 In contrast to prediction Ia, there was no evidence that female breeders load-lighten during the egg-
14 phase: they did not decrease their egg volume in response to a change in the number of female
15 helpers (Figures 2a & c, Table 1a), although groups with more female helpers tended to have
16 smaller eggs (Table 1a, mean no. ♀ helpers). As predicted, we found no evidence that female
17 breeders decrease their egg volume with a changing number of male helpers (Figure 2b & c; Table
18 1a). In line with prediction Ib, females laid larger clutches with an increasing number of helpers of
19 both sexes (Figure 2d) and this was likely a plastic response (Table 1b, within-subject effect no.
20 helpers was significant.). The effect of the number of helpers on clutch size and egg volume did not
21 vary among years, with rainfall, or between inexperienced and experienced females (Table 1).
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37 *Helper effects on future prospects: re-nest interval and annual survival*

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39 In contrast to prediction II, there is no evidence that re-nest intervals were shorter as the number of
40 males that helped provisioning the preceding nest increased (Table 2, model 2 vs. model 1; Figure
41 2e). There is some evidence that groups with more male helpers generally have shorter re-nest
42 intervals than groups with fewer males, although this effect was rather small (0.6 days; Table 2,
43 model 1 vs. model 4). Interestingly, an increase in female helpers that helped provision the previous
44 nest allowed breeder females to reduce the re-nest interval (figure 2e), and including the interaction
45 between the number of female helpers and whether the previous nest hatched was supported by the
46 data ($\Delta AIC_c = 2.8$). There was no evidence that either male or female helpers have different effects
47 on experienced and unexperienced mothers ($\Delta AIC_c = 3.6$), or that the effects of helpers varied
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1 among years ($\Delta AIC_c > 12$).

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4 Helper but not breeder survival decreased with an increasing number of female helpers (Fig
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6 3, Table 3, interaction status \times no. ♀ helpers), but there was no evidence that the number of male
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8 helpers affected survival of either helpers or breeders (Fig. 3, Table 3, model 5 vs. model 1). To test
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10 whether the effects of male and female helpers on survival were different, the number of male and
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12 female helpers in model 1 was substituted by group size. However, this model was not better
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14 supported by the data ($\Delta AIC_c = +8.4$). This indicates that helper survival was affected differentially
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16 by the number of male and female helpers, thus supporting prediction IIIa.
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Discussion

The questions of whether and how helpers improve the fitness of their recipients is of crucial importance for a complete understanding of the evolution of cooperative breeding. However, it has proved difficult to determine helper effects, because of the difficulty in determining causation when larger group sizes might be associated with better quality territories. Here we made an attempt to disentangle helper effects from possible confounds of group size and quality. First, due to differences in provisioning behaviour (load-lightening in groups with male helpers, additive care in groups with female helpers) our predictions varied with the sex of the helpers rather than overall group size. Second, by having multiple measurements per individual, our dataset allowed us to separate effects due to changes in group composition from consistent differences between groups. We found no evidence for concealed helper effects via reduced maternal investment in egg size. An increase in the number of helpers did allow females to lay larger clutches and an increase in female helpers was associated with quicker re-nesting. However, helper survival decreased as the number of female helpers increased. Our results also indicate that there are differences among groups. Groups with more female helpers tended to lay smaller eggs, whereas groups with more male helpers had slightly shorter re-nest intervals and survived better.

Absence of concealed helper effects on maternal investment

We did not find evidence for concealed helper effects: breeding females did not adjust the size of their eggs in response to the number of female helpers, not even in some specific years (as suggested by Koenig et al. 2009). The absence of egg size adjustment was surprising since nestlings receive more food in the presence of female helpers (Brouwer et al. 2014a), thus any negative effects of reduced egg investment would be compensated during the nestling phase. Interestingly, egg size was associated to other environmental conditions like rainfall (likely reflecting food availability; Table 1), although this might not be active adjustment by females, but rather a consequence of inferior conditions. A possibility remains that other unmeasured components of egg

1 quality (e.g. nutritional content) were strategically adjusted by the female in response to the number
2 of female helpers.
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6 In their model, Savage et al. (2015) showed that mothers are expected to reduce pre-birth
7 investment whenever pre-birth investment and post-birth are substitutable, as this reduction can be
8 compensated by the carers later. However, maternal tactics will be less important when group size
9 or helper helpfulness is unpredictable at the time when the mother produces the offspring. Brouwer
10 et al. (2014a) previously hypothesised that lower reliability of female helpers might explain the
11 absence of load-lightening in their presence, and the same could be true for investment in egg size.
12 Since female helpers disperse on average earlier than males and can also initiate their own nest,
13 help delivered by females might be less predictable. Therefore, it may be more risky to make
14 investment decisions predicated on their presence (Brouwer et al. 2014a).
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26 Load-lightening during the egg phase seems to be common in cooperative breeders. In five
27 of the six species studied so far (including the congener species *M. cyaneus*), egg size was reduced
28 in the presence of helpers (Russell et al. 2007; Taborsky et al. 2007; Canestrari et al. 2011; Santos
29 and Macedo 2011; Paquet et al. 2013; but see Koenig et al. 2009). It is interesting to note that had
30 we not specifically investigated whether changes in helper number resulted in changes in egg
31 volume within the same female, we would erroneously have concluded that, as predicted, egg
32 volume was reduced in the presence of female helpers, since groups with more female helpers were
33 associated with smaller egg size.
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45 46 *Helper effects on current reproduction*

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48 As predicted, breeding females did lay larger clutches in response to an increasing number of
49 helpers. Although increased clutch size has been shown to increase with an increase in exclusive
50 male carers in the cooperatively polyandrous dunnoek (Davies and Hatchwell 1992) and with the
51 number of helpers in the cooperatively breeding apostlebird (Woxvold and Magrath 2005), such
52 increases have not been commonly reported among cooperative breeders with philopatric helpers-
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1 at-the-nest. We have shown that this association was a plastic response in red-winged fairy-wren.
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3 Increased offspring production by females is expected when production costs are cheap relative to
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5 those of the rearing period (Savage et al. 2013). Because moving from two to three eggs potentially
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7 represents a 50% increase in annual fecundity, this suggests strong fitness benefits from helping.
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9 However, the association between fledgling production and the number of female or male helpers
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11 was quite weak (Figure 3d in Brouwer et al. 2014a), almost certainly because productivity is
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13 strongly determined by high rates of predation.
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18 19 *Helper effects on future prospects*

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21 In contrast to our predictions, female but not male helpers allowed breeding females to reduce the
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23 re-nest interval after the preceding nest reached the nestling stage. Despite the increased workload
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25 experienced during the previous attempt, breeding females reduced their re-nest interval with the
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27 prospect of raising a brood with extra female help at hand. Reducing the re-nest interval by more
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29 than 3 days per additional helper female could enable breeding females to have an extra nesting
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31 attempt within the same breeding season and thus potentially increase her annual reproductive
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33 success.
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37 Our results were consistent with a survival benefit caused by load-lightening at the nestling
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39 stage, although only for helpers. However, this positive effect of load-lightening is counterbalanced
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41 by a survival cost due to increased competition, as the net effect of an increasing number of male
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43 helpers is zero. The number of female helpers was negatively associated with helper survival, which
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45 is consistent with an absence of survival benefits of female helpers in combination with a negative
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47 effect of increased competition in larger groups (Figure 1d). Intra-group competition could result
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49 from increased competition for food (Brouwer et al. 2006; Brouwer et al. 2009), and helpers might
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51 incur a higher cost of competition than dominants because breeders are better foragers or in better
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53 condition. Helpers may also suffer more from additive care because they undergo more energetic
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55 costs than breeders when helping (Heinsohn & Legge 1999, Hatchwell et al. 2014). An alternative
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1 explanation for our result would be that there is no measureable survival benefit from load-
2 lightening, instead, helpers suffer from increased competition from female helpers. However, we do
3 not have any indication why intra-group competition would increase with more female, but not
4 male helpers.
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10 In superb fairy-wrens, breeding females benefit from helping by having higher survival as a
11 result of egg size reduction (Cockburn et al. 2008; Russell et al. 2007), but there is no evidence that
12 breeding males benefit from helping and it is unknown what the effects on other helpers are. In red-
13 winged fairy-wrens females increase clutch size with the number of helpers, which can result in
14 increased current reproductive success and therefore also benefits males, although to a lesser extent
15 due to the presence of high rates of extra-pair offspring (Brouwer et al. 2011). The reduced helper
16 survival with an increasing number of female helpers will also affect group size the next season and
17 therefore future reproductive success of the group. Future work integrating the different fitness
18 components will have to show whether the increased benefits through increased reproductive
19 success (and thus group size) will outweigh the negative effects female helpers have on helper
20 survival.
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37 *Disentangling helper effects from possible confounds of group size*

38 Our results indicated that there are differences among groups that were not a plastic response to a
39 changing group composition. Differences among groups of varying sizes could be the result of
40 underlying quality differences when certain high quality individuals/territories are more likely to be
41 successful and thus are also more likely to have larger groups. We found that groups with more
42 males survived better and re-nested slightly sooner, whereas groups with more females tended to lay
43 smaller eggs. If our results were simply due to differences in quality then the associations would be
44 expected to occur for both sexes, unless certain conditions result in the accumulation of female, but
45 not male helpers and vice versa. Since females disperse on average earlier than males, an
46 accumulation of males could be the result of locally adverse dispersal conditions. However, adverse
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1 dispersal conditions must be associated with high breeder survival, suggesting good conditions,
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3 which are then expected to result in accumulation of female helpers as well.
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6 An alternative explanation for our findings is that because males disperse on average later
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8 than females, groups with more males are more stable than groups with fewer males. This could
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10 result in higher group survival and allow females to re-nest sooner. Why female breeders with more
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12 female helpers lay smaller eggs remains unknown, possibly such an effect could be the result from
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14 sex-ratio biases due to females hatching from smaller eggs. Whether this is true and whether there
15
16 are any other biases in offspring sex-ratio related to the sex of the helpers present on the territory
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18 remains to be investigated.
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Figure legends:

Figure 1. Predictions of the effects of male (grey line) and female (black line) helpers on a). egg volume and re-nest interval, b). clutch size, c & d). survival of males and helper females, e & f). survival of breeder females. Note that we predict that $a > b$ if breeder females reduce their egg size, and thus benefit from having female helpers too.

Figure 2. The distribution of the within-female change in egg volume shown for a change in the number of a). female and b). male helpers. The relation between the number of female (black) and male (grey) helpers for c). egg volume, d). clutch size and e). the re-nest interval after nest failure for groups where the previous nest reached the nestling stage corrected for effects of year and helpers of the other sex. Also shown is the observed distribution of egg volumes (f). Numbers indicate the sample sizes for the number of female (upper) and male (lower) helpers with symbol sizes adjusted accordingly. Lines show the predictions of the within-subject effects of the models from Table 1 (Fig. 1c,d) and Table 2 (Fig. 1e). Error bars are the SEM.

Figure 3. Annual survival in relation to the number of female and male helpers in the group for a). female breeders, b). male breeders, c). female helpers and d). male helpers. Numbers indicate the sample sizes for the number of female (upper) and male (lower) helpers with the symbol sizes adjusted accordingly. Lines show the predictions of model 1 from Table 3. Error bars are the SEM.

Table 1. Results of a multivariate GLMM examining a). egg volume and b). clutch size. Egg volume was standardized into z-scores before analysis (mean=1.50cm³ ± 0.12cm³ SD, N=292). The no. of (fe)male helpers indicates the within-subject effect whereas the mean no. of (fe)male helpers represents the between-subject effect. The effects included in the final model are shaded in grey.

Parameter	a). Egg volume (identity link)					b). Clutch Size (logit link)				
	estimate	s.e.	χ^2	d.f.	P	Estimate	s.e.	χ^2	d.f.	P
<i>Fixed effects</i>										
intercept	-0.305	0.494	-	1	-	2.122	0.494	-	1	-
no. ♂ helpers	-0.041	0.059	0.50	1	0.48	0.488	0.155	9.87	1	0.002
mean no. ♂ helpers	0.046	0.113	0.17	1	0.68	-0.167	0.331	0.26	1	0.61
no. ♀ helpers	0.046	0.067	0.43	1	0.51	0.776	0.240	10.5	1	0.001
mean no. ♀ helpers	-0.312	0.163	3.65	1	0.056	0.238	0.471	0.25	1	0.62
tarsus length of breeding ♀	0.159	0.128	1.55	1	0.21	-0.018	0.234	0.01	1	0.92
day of season	0.0045	0.0019	5.70	1	0.017	-0.047	0.007	41.0	1	<0.001
rainfall	-0.126	0.058	4.83	1	0.028	-0.145	0.279	0.27	1	0.60
breeding experience dominant ♀	0.205	0.100	4.19	1	0.041	0.694	0.383	3.29	1	0.070
year	-	-	9.11	4	0.58	-	-	4.36	4	0.36
no. ♂ helpers × rainfall	0.013	0.029	0.19	1	0.66	-0.024	0.135	0.03	1	0.86
no. ♀ helpers × rainfall	0.028	0.055	0.25	1	0.62	0.143	0.392	0.13	1	0.72
no. ♂ helpers × breeding experience ♀	0.067	0.075	0.80	1	0.37	0.008	0.199	0.01	1	0.92
no. ♀ helpers × breeding experience ♀	0.113	0.249	0.21	1	0.65	1.503	1.007	2.23	1	0.14
no. ♂ helpers × year	-	-	2.92	4	0.57	-	-	0.78	4	0.94
no. ♀ helpers × year	-	-	2.55	4	0.64	-	-	2.23	4	0.69
observer	-	-	4.93	5	0.42	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Random effects</i>										
Variance among breeding ♀♀	0.797	0.124	-	1	-	0.590	0.329	-	1	-
Residual variance	0.213	0.022	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Covariance breeding ♀ level	-0.166	0.163	-	1	-	-0.166	0.163	-	1	-
Correlation residual level	-0.143	0.032	-	1	-	-0.143	0.032	-	1	-

Note that covariance estimates are given in columns of both dependent variables. The covariance equals the correlation multiplied by the product of the square roots of the residual variances of egg volume and clutch size.

Table 2. Summary of model selection on the re-nest interval after nest failure (N = 267) showing the coefficients with S.E.. The no. of (fe)male helpers indicates the within-subject effect whereas the mean no. of (fe)male helpers represents the between-subject effect. Year is included as a fixed categorical factor in all models.

Model	Intercept	Hatched*	No. ♀ helpers	Mean no. ♀ helpers	No. ♂ helpers	Mean no. ♂ helpers	Hatched × no. ♀ helpers	Hatched × no. ♂ helpers	Experience dom. ♀ ⁺	No. par.	Deviance	ΔAIC _c
1	10.1±1.31	1.55±0.62	1.36±1.58	-	-	-0.65±0.35	-4.20±1.93	-	-	13	1582.3	0
2	10.2±1.31	1.57±0.62	1.39±1.57	-	-0.41±0.93	-0.65±0.35	-4.55±1.92	1.85±1.20	-	15	1578.6	0.9
3	10.1±1.31	1.56±0.62	1.27±1.58	-	0.68±0.61	-0.64±0.35	-4.27±1.92	-	-	14	1581.0	1.0
4	9.54±1.28	1.57±0.62	1.26±1.59	-	-	-	-4.10±1.94	-	-	12	1585.6	1.1
5	9.52±1.46	1.52±0.62	1.35±1.57	-	-	-0.61±0.35	-4.20±1.92	-	0.69±0.73	14	1581.4	1.3
6	9.48±1.49	1.53±0.62	1.38±1.57	-	-	-0.61±0.35	-4.56±1.92	1.88±1.20	0.82±0.73	15	1577.4	1.9

*Reference category is unhatched. ⁺Reference category is inexperienced.

Table 3. Summary of model selection on annual adult survival of red-winged fairy-wrens (N=1715) showing the coefficients with S.E. on the logit scale. The no. of (fe)male helpers indicates the within-subject effect whereas the mean no. of (fe)male helpers represents the between-subject effect.

Year is included as a fixed categorical factor in all models.

M	Intercept	Status ⁺	Sex*	No. ♀ helpers	Mean no. ♀ helpers	No. ♂ helpers	Mean no. ♂ helpers	Sex* × no. ♀ helpers	Status ⁺ × no. ♀ helpers	Sex* × status ⁺	Sex* × status ⁺ × no. ♀ helpers	No. par.	Deviance	ΔAIC _c
1	1.27±0.22	-0.10± 0.13	-0.19±0.12	-0.36±0.11	-	-	0.20±0.09	-	0.43±0.16	-	-	13	1911.4	0
2	1.26±0.23	-0.07± 0.16	-0.31±0.24	-0.51±0.16	-	-	0.20±0.09	0.33±0.24	0.83±0.24	0.08±0.28	0.79±0.34	16	1905.8	0.5
3	1.20±0.21	-0.14± 0.12	-	-0.41±0.11	-	-	0.21±0.09	-	0.48±0.16	-	-	12	1913.9	0.5
4	1.32±0.23	-0.11± 0.13	-0.18±0.12	-0.36±0.11	-0.09±0.13	-	0.20±0.09	-	0.42±0.16	-	-	14	1910.9	1.6
5	1.29±0.22	-0.11± 0.13	-0.20±0.12	-0.36±0.11	-	-0.05 ±0.08	0.20±0.09	-	0.43±0.16	-	-	14	1910.9	1.6
6	1.27±0.23	-0.15± 0.12	-	-0.40±0.11	-0.12±0.13	-	0.21±0.09	-	0.46±0.16	-	-	13	1913.1	1.8
7	1.25±0.23	-0.07± 0.16	-0.14±0.16	-0.38±0.12	-	-	0.20±0.09	-	0.44±0.17	-0.08±0.25	-	14	1911.3	1.9
8	1.28±0.22	-0.11± 0.13	-0.18±0.12	-0.34±0.14	-	-	0.20±0.09	-0.04±0.16	0.43±0.16	-	-	14	1911.3	2.0

⁺ Reference category is helper. *Reference category is male.

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Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

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No. male or female helpers